

COMPATIBILITY OF PROGRESSIVE GLASSES IN RELATION TO AGE, REFRACTIVE ERROR AND OCCUPATION OF PATIENT

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ABSTRACT:

Today's generation do not accept any limitation with visual function. Usually by the age of 40 the normal human lens starts losing its elasticity affecting eyes' ability to focus on near objects usually causing presbyopia. One comprehensive study on "Global vision impairment due to uncorrected presbyopia" estimate that 1.04 billion people in the world experience vision impairment caused by presbyopia. The study also revealed that an estimated 517 million had no eyeglasses or inappropriate eyeglasses. As a result their ability to complete important daily task is restricted. Lens design is selected such that patient's ability to perform daily activities like reading, driving and computer use meets. Today's progressive lenses have better optics and fewer peripheral aberrations, making them very comfortable for active wear. Some of the newest high definition lens designs found in modern progressive lens is created with the same wave front-guided technology used in LASIK surgery for crystal optical performance over a wide field of view¹.

Thus the aim of the present study was to find out the compatibility of progressive glasses in relation to age, refractive status, lens design and occupation of the patient. These findings will assist the eye care practitioner to understand and convey to patients the potential difficulties associated with wearing progressive lenses.

Keywords: Presbyopia, Progressive Lenses, Refractive Status, Occupation and Age

INTRODUCTION:

PROGRESSIVE ADDITION LENSES:

Since the introduction given by Essilor in 1959, progressive addition lenses have gained worldwide acceptance as the most preferred ophthalmic lenses for the correction of presbyopia because they provide comfortable vision at all distances. The lenses also have the advantage of appearing like single vision lenses and so look much better than any bifocal or trifocal which have the obvious lines and ledges of the segs.

THE CONCEPT OF A PROGRESSIVE ADDITION LENS²

A progressive addition lens provides areas for distance and near vision that are relatively stable in power and free of distortion. These areas are joined by a corridor of increasing plus power, useful for focusing from distance to near.

The distance and near zones and the corridor of transitional power are generated by a gradual increase in the curvature of the front surface of the lens. A typical lens PAL front surface shape can be represented as a series of conic sections which are stacked one upon the other. By joining these sections with their apices coinciding, astigmatism free corridor of increasing plus power results.

From the distance portion to the near portion, the conics sections vary from ellipse, to circles, to parabolas, to hyperbolas. Where the sections coincide, front surface is free of astigmatism. Where the conic sections do not coincide, front surface astigmatism results. The intensity and orientation of the astigmatism varies with the distance from the corridor and depends on the lens design. Depending on the lens design, the peripheral astigmatic area will cause blurred or distorted vision to varying degrees.⁶

The intensity of peripheral astigmatism varies largely between different lens designs. A lens design which spreads the astigmatic surface changes over a larger area of the periphery will have a smaller optically pure near zone but more gradual boundaries are classified as “soft” designs. For those designs with larger near zones, the trade off is a higher level of surface astigmatism at the boundary and beyond into the peripheral at the boundary are classified as “hard” designs.³

The same concept holds for the design feature of corridor length. A shorter corridor results from a more rapid transition from the distance power to the designated near power. This rapid change in power is generated by changing the front surface curvature by a large amount over a small area of the lens. The result will be a higher level of astigmatism in the peripheral areas of the lens and therefore a hard design. Likewise, a longer corridor will result when the transition from the distance power to the designated near power occurs over a larger area of the lens. The more gradual transition results in a softer design.

Differences in the sizes of the distance and the near zones, the length and width of the corridor, and the distribution of front surface astigmatism are the primary design features which distinguish one PAL design from another. Patient preference for one design over another will depend on the lens which results from the compromise between zone sizes and levels of peripheral distortion.^{4,5,6.}

METHODOLOGY:

RESEARCH DESIGN:

The present study has been a questionnaire based a prospective, randomized study which was carried out from July, 2014 to April, 2015 at K. P. Shangvi (Shree Bharatimaiya College of Optometry and Physiotherapy), Surat to find out the adaptability of progressive addition lenses according to refractive status of the patient, occupation of the patient and to compare the adaptability with standard progressive lens design and advanced design.

OBJECTIVES:

To evaluate the compatibility of progressive glasses in relation to:

- Refractive status of the patient
- Working area of the patient
- Standard lens design and advanced lens design
- The common adaptation problems

Participants:

All the progressive lens spectacle wearers were recruited as healthy volunteers to participate in the study.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Best corrected visual acuity 6/6 or 6/9.
- Patients above 40 years of age of any gender.
- Patients having different occupations with usage of computer in their daily routine
- Patients having pseudophakia with no other ocular abnormality.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Best corrected vision worst than 6/9.
- Age below 40 years. Occasional spectacle wearer.
- Patients having other organic eye problems.
- Patients having outdoors sports activities which need excessive head movements.
- Mentally retarders and patients having facial asymmetry.

Pretested questionnaire was given to 84 patients with progressive addition lenses as per inclusion criteria and their responses were collected. Confidentially and privacy of patients has also been maintained. Various types of occupations were categorized with priority of their usage of working distance such as intermediate, distance and near work. Various types of refractive errors were also categorized with mainly three types: Hypermetropic, myopia and simple presbyopia to avoid the complexity in results. Design of progressive was determined from the patient's responses like cost of lenses, authenticity card of product, local brand and sometimes by seeing the logo of product. To avoid complexity of results researchers have categorized the design in standard and advanced according to features provided by particular brand like intermediate zone and peripheral aberration. All responses were analyzed with the help of statistics using chi-square test.

RESULTS:

Table 1: Age and Gender Distribution of 84 Progressive Glasses User

Age group	Male	Female	Total
40-44	9	9	18
45-49	14	8	22
50-54	20	8	28
55-59	5	8	13
60-64	2	1	3
Total	50	34	84

Graph: 1

The present study has observed 59.52 per cent males and 40.47 per cent females. The Graph: 1 shows that maximum numbers of patients were found in age group 45-54 years because this was actually a working age group who need visual

function at their working task best. Researchers have also observed that maximum numbers of females were found in age group between 40-59 years.

Table: 2 Refractive Status of Patient and Adaptation of Progressive Addition Lens:

Adaptation Time	Type of Refractive Error			
	H	M	SP	Total
A	43	14	4	61
B	14	6	3	23
total	57	20	7	84

(Here A = 1-5 days, B= 5-10days, C=>15 days H= Hypermetropia , M = Myopia and SP = Simple- Presbyopia)

Graph: 2 shows the adaptation time needed to progressive addition lens wearer in different types of refractive errors i.e., Hypermetropia, myopia and simple presbyopia. Here from the results it has been observed that myopic patients need more time to adapt than Hypermetropic patients. With the help of statistics by using chi-square test it has been found the p-value 5.991 and therefore there is a significant difference between adaptation time and refractive status of the patient. Schultz DN et. al. study on factors influencing patient acceptance of varilux 2 lenses shows that hyperopic wearers exhibited an acceptance rate (81.8%) that was substantially higher than emmetropic (68.8%) and myopic (63.6%). The findings of the present study shows that about 26.08 per cent of myopic patients need more than 5 days for adaptation and about 70.49 per cent of hypermetropic patients get adapt within 5 days. In simple presbyopia the adaptation time is variable which could be due to some other factors.

Table 3: Computer and Progressive Lens Adaptation

Working duration on Computer in Hours	Adaptation Time		
	A	B	Total
2	27	4	31
4	16	7	23
≥6	19	11	30
total	62	22	84

There is a significant difference in adaptation time in patients with various working hours on computer (p value = 4.72). Patients who have to work 6 hours or more than 6 hours/day computer work need more time to get adapt to progressive glasses.

Table: 4 Progressive Lens Deign and Adaptation

Adaptation time	Design		
	Advanced	Standard	Totals
A	39	23	62
B	6	16	22
Totals	45	39	84

From the above graph it can be seen that patients need comparatively more time to adapt regular design. It has further clearly noticed that only 7 per cent patients needs more than 15 days for adaptation in advanced design whereas in case of standard lens design there are 19 per cent patients who needs more than 15 days to get adapted. But this difference is not statistically significant (p -value = 3.84) may be because of law sample size, unawareness of patients about their lens design or indirect judgment of design.

In Dalzell (1979) et al. study the preference between varilux 2 and American optical ultravue progressive addition lenses were observed and it states that patients progressive addition lenses were on served and it states that patients preferred varilux 2 lenses. Brookman (1988) et al. study reveals that patients preferred Seiko lens which have reduced peripheral distortions. Krefman (1991) et al. study states that multi design lens scored highest in the quality of vision, ease of adaptation and patients' satisfaction.

All these studies shows that steps by step improvements in design of progressive lens can make adaptation more easier mainly because of reduction of peripheral aberration and smoothness of design. The present study compares

the standard design with advanced design which has very minimum peripheral aberration and on the basis of findings also it has been found that advanced design is comparatively easy for adaptation.

CONCLUSION:

Hypermetropic patients can easily get adapted to the progressive addition lenses. Patients with job requirement of either farther or near working distance got easily adapted to any design of progressive lenses however occupations which demands for intermediate distance were better with advanced or specially designed progressive lenses and this design can also help in minimizing the common adaptation problems like sideway looking and reading newspaper so far.

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